

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE - EELISA MULTI LABS (SHARING FACILITIES & EQUIPMENT)

Deliverable 4.4 Coordinated infrastructure strategy

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the work made in WP4 *EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)*.

The objective of the Task 4.3: Coordination of new local infrastructures was to identify the funding opportunities at local, regional, national, and European level in order to identify possible joint actions in the future.

This mapping aims also to provide more information to researchers willing to submit proposals and facilitate discussions about bidding. It turned out that there are very few funding opportunities for starting (ie. “buying”) research infrastructure and that institutions face very different local and national situations that do not facilitate coordination of new initiatives.

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Responsibles for WP4

Partner	Acronym	Contact person for WP4
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Scuola Normale Superiore	SNS	Mr Pasqualantonio PINGUE, Manager of Research & Innovation AREA and CCO at NEST Laboratory
Scuola Superiore Di Studi Universitari E Di Perfezionamento S Anna	SSSA	Mrs. Rossella RASO, Project Manager
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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

Research Infrastructures. The term “Research infrastructures” includes any piece of equipment that might be available to ‘customer’ whether they are in a laboratory (commercial device or developed/customed by researchers themselves), on a platform.

Research Structures. The term “Research Structures” includes the research centres, research hubs, research groups and research labs, institutes with a research focus, which produce significant research outcomes and thereby, represent a R&I capacity.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 44 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a collective strategic research area and research infrastructure map (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 Rationale

Following the mapping and the preliminary results of WP4 (roadmap of research infrastructures), the aim of this task is to help EELISA partners in identifying common needs for local research facilities. In that phase the funding allocated for the research facility is still local: there is no joint funding between partners, but just a coordination of the local acquisition to avoid doubling infrastructures. The list of these additional facilities available on the booking system (D4.4) will be regularly updated on a voluntary and bottom-up approach.

Beside optimizing the equipment within the consortium and allowing for a larger public interested in each facility, this task aims at enabling partners to strengthen their capacity to attract local (regional/national) funding by arguing for a European dimension of these new facilities, de facto accessible and of declared interest for different institutions within EELISA.

3 Processes of collection

The main activity of this task was to identify funding opportunities for research infrastructures.

Each member has been tasked to identify local or national opportunities so that at EELISA level we can have an overview of all available calls for research infrastructures. This has been the opportunity to exchange about how institutions can set up new facilities in their premises. This work has been done during autumn 2023 and is presented in Annex 1.

The list is only composed of calls whose main objective is to fund research infrastructures or equipment. While it is quite often possible to fund equipment via regular research projects, the scope of this work was to focus on dedicated funding for research infrastructures.

4 Outcomes

The main outcome of the task is that Alliance members are facing very different situations with regards to research infrastructure funding. Defining a comprehensive strategy at EELISA level based on such variety of situations is challenging as its implementation would largely depend on elements that Institutions cannot control.

For instance, while there is barely French national funding for universities to start new infrastructures, Romania used European Structural Funds to support them, and Germany does have a programme through the DFG. Some universities such as UPM have their own programme to support researchers.

We notice that not all EELISA countries are represented: Hungary and Italy do not have such funding per se. Worth noticing that, in Italy, there were opportunities thanks to The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) but such initiative is not likely to be repeated in the future².

Nevertheless, this list remains important to develop a strategy for EELISA. Indeed, the monitoring of calls will be a part of EELISA phase 2 especially when InnoCORE will end (May 2024). Until then, the members of the WP will keep sharing information about funding. Upon identification of an opportunities, members will be able to share it and evaluate the added value to involve other EELISA members to strengthen the proposal.

² See: <https://www.gea.mur.gov.it/Bandi/IR#definitive> (in Italian)

In a more general perspective, another use of this work is to highlight the diversity in different institutions and countries and to advocate for more compatible funding between them. The next step of the work within EELISA InnoCORE is to consider joint infrastructures. Without relevant funding, their implementation will face additional burdens.

Finally, this approach may also serve to request funding in specific areas where a need has been identified by EELISA, but for which a sufficient mass of users is not present in one specific country. In this case, the European dimension via EELISA will bring a critical asset to a proposal by supporting the institution in its capacity to be a leader in a certain area and by involving other European colleagues.

5 Conclusion

Given the heterogeneity of the research infrastructure funding landscape and the scarcity of funding in some Member States, the Alliance will keep monitoring the funding opportunities and ease the circulation of information. By doing so, when a member prepares a proposal, it could add or demonstrate support from other members on a voluntary basis and hence demonstrate a greater critical mass of potential users. This will be the first implementation of a coordinated infrastructure strategy.

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Annex 1 – Mapping of opportunities

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Country	Funder name	Type of funder	Title of the call (orig)	Title of the call (EN)	Reference of the call	Short description in English	SRA	Deadline(s)	Budget of the call	Average size of a proposal	Eligible costs (summary)	Funding rate	Source of co-funding	of participants and partners	Additional information	website
FR	Région Ile-de-France	Regional	SESAME - Équipements et plateformes scientifiques et technologiques	SESAME - Scientific and technological equipment and platforms		The main aim of the SESAME programme is to make the Paris Region a world leader in science and technology by giving laboratories the resources they need to develop new projects and set up original experimental research facilities. This call for projects is consistent with other regional funding tools for scientific equipment, including the State-Region Plan Contract, the regionalised PIA (SESAME filière PIA), Genopole, the Major Research and Innovation Areas and the ERDF operational programme. By co-financing cutting-edge equipment and shared platforms open to the scientific community, as well as to companies in the Paris Region, the Region is helping to structure the various centres of excellence in the Paris Region and make them more attractive.	Any	May/June each year	Not defined	between 0,2M€ and 3M€ for the price of the equipment (excl. VAT)	Purchase of equipment (no maintenance)	66% except in Social Sciences and Humanities where it is 100%	Public or Private	Projects should come from Higher Education institution based in the Region and have a regional dimension but support from other EU partner is possible and would be an added value during the evaluation of the proposal (letter of support)	This call has been running for 30 years	https://www.iledefrance.fr/sesame-equipements-et-plateformes-scientifiques-et-technologiques
TR	TÜBİTAK	National	1000-Üniversitelerin Araştırma ve Geliştirme Potansiyelinin Artırılmasına Yönelik Destek Programı	1000 - Funding Program for improving R&D Potential of Universities		The purpose of this programme is to support projects under the scope of the calls specified to improve Research & Development potential of universities.	Any	Depending on call	Upper limit for budget and other requirements are specified in call text.	specified in call text.		100%				
TR	TÜBİTAK	National	1001 - Bilimsel ve Teknolojik Araştırma Projelerini Destekleme Programı	1001 - The Scientific and Technological Research Projects Funding Program		The purpose of this program is to support research projects that comply with scientific principles for generating new information, making scientific comments or solving technological problems.		March/September each year	The requested budget from TÜBİTAK can be maximum 1.650.000 TRY	The budget requested for machine/equipment should be balanced with the total budget	The budget requested for machine/equipment should be balanced with the total budget.	100%				
TR	TÜBİTAK	National	1505 - Üniversite-Sanayi İşbirliği Destek Programı	1505 - University – Industry Collaboration Support Program		With this program, it is aimed to contribute to the commercialization of the knowledge and technology in universities, research infrastructure, public research centers and institutes by transforming them into products or processes and transferring them to the industry, in line with the needs of organizations located in Turkey and committed to implementing the project results in Turkey. In the application principles of the program; The private sector organization, referred to as the Client Organization, and the university, research infrastructure or public research center and institute, referred to as the Executing Organization, will sign a Cooperation Agreement. To be carried out by the Executing Organization within the framework of this agreement; The project of producing a new product, developing or improving an existing product, increasing the product quality or standard, or developing new cost-reducing techniques and new production technologies will be financed by TÜBİTAK and the Customer Organization.		any time	The requested budget from TÜBİTAK can be maximum 1.500.000 TRY		Personnel costs Contract staff Scholarship Travel costs Instrument/Equipment/Software/Broadcasting costs Service costs Material costs	100 % for Universities; 75 % for SME, 40% for industrial partners		Projects should involve a technology provider (University, Research Infrastructures, Public Research Centers, and Institutes) and a client (large firm or SME).		
ES	Vice-Rectorate for Research, Innovation and Doctoral Studies "Programa Propio de I+D+i"	National	Convocatoria de ayudas para la cofinanciación de infraestructuras de I+D+i de la UPM	Call for grants for the cofinancing of R&D&I infrastructures of the UPM	N/A	Applicants: UPM principal investigators of projects funded under public national or regional R&I calls, where the call does not fund 100% of the cost of the equipment. The call has two strands: Strand 1. Co-financing of equipment with a cost between 15,000€ and 85,000€ (this figure can vary) (excluding VAT) purchased within the framework of projects funded under certain public national or regional competitive calls. The equipment must have been purchased during the year of the UPM call (e.g. for the 2022 call, the equipment must have been acquired in 2022). Strand 2. Under this strand, UPM funds the annual depreciation (for the year of the call, i.e. for 2022 the depreciation of 2022 according to the depreciation schedule) of equipments purchased under the national Ministry call for acquisition of equipment and infrastructure (Convocatoria de adquisición de equipamiento científico-técnico, del subprograma estatal de infraestructuras de investigación y equipamiento científico técnico). See below.	Any	Yearly basis	Variable depending the year (70,000€ in 2023 and 300,000€ in 2022)	17 000 €	Strand 1. Co-financing of equipment purchased with other public national or local competitive calls. UPM will fund between 50% to 100% of the non-funded amount. E.g. if the equipment cost is 40,000€ and the European, national or local call funded 20,000€, the grant by the UPM call will fund the "balance" (partially or totally), between 10,000 and 20,000€. Strand 2. Payment of the annual depreciation fee of equipments purchased under a specific national call (annual fee for the year of the call according to the depreciation schedule).	between 50% to 100%	National and regional calls for R&I projects	Preference is given to equipments and infrastructure shared by several research groups at UPM, and not owned and used by only one research group. (No international partnerships are possible).	UPM Research Commission will decide the co-funding ratio (%) in case the call budget does not cover the total amount of all applications.	https://www.upm.es/Investigacion/Programa_Propio_UPM/2022/Infraestructuras?id=489ed092960d3810VgnVCM1000009c7648a_&fmt=detail
ES	Ministry for Science and Innovation, Spanish State Research Agency	National	Subprograma Estatal de Infraestructuras de Investigación y Equipamiento Científico-Técnico	State sub-programme for research infrastructures and scientific and technical equipment		Funding for the purchasing of state-of-the-art scientific and technical equipment by R&I entities. "Scientific and technical equipment" means any physical means (equipment or instruments) needed for carrying out research, including accessories and ancillary components. It includes the facility itself as far as it complies with the aforementioned definition (physical mean necessary for carrying out research). The equipment can be a single piece or several pieces (distributed). In case of distributed infrastructures, the grant will cover only those located in the same location. The call covers state-of-the-art equipment which is complex and very specialized, its purchasing, building and setting up. Applicants must be public non-profit research entities with its own legal personality, legally established in Spain. Networks are excluded. The total investment cost for each project of scientific and technical equipment must be equal or higher than 400,000€ and equal or lower than 1,500,000€.	Any	Annual call	Aprox. 187M€	Between 400 000€ to 1.5M€	Direct costs directly linked with the purchasing and setting up of scientific and technical equipment (purchasing, transport, building, rollout, putting into service, licences).	Up to 100% of the direct costs.	2021 call Next generation 2019 ERDF 2018 ERDF	Applicants must be public research institutions legally established in Spain.		https://www.aei.gov.es/en/subprogram/state-subprogram-research-infrastructures-and-scientific-technical-equipment
ES	Ministry for Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation	National	UNICO I+D 6G 2022 Subprograma de infraestructuras de investigación y equipamiento científico-técnico en el ámbito de las tecnologías 5G avanzado y 6G	UNICO I+D 6G 2022 State sub-programme for research infrastructures and scientific and technical equipment in the field of advanced 5G technologies and 6G		Funding for the purchasing of state-of-the-art scientific and technical equipment in the field of advanced 5G technologies and 6G: purchasing, building, transport, rollout, putting into service, upgrade and improvement. The infrastructures cannot be used for commercial purposes. There call also has obligations for the beneficiaries regarding sharing the infrastructures with other entities (obligations of shared use).	Any	Ad hoc call	23M€	Between 300 000€ and 2M€	Direct costs directly linked with the purchasing and setting up of scientific and technical equipment (purchasing, transport, building, rollout, putting into service, licences).	The grant could cover up to 100% of the direct costs. Final rate depends on actual fundable cost of the proposal and the total available budget.	Recovery and Resilience Facility, NextGenerationEU	Applicants must be public research entities, public universities, other public R&I centers, established in Spain, part of the institutional public sector.		https://portalayudas.mineco.gob.es/Convocatoria-Ayudas-6G-2022/Paginas/Index.aspx
EU	HEU	European	Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership	Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-DEV-01	Expected Outcome: Projects are expected to contribute to all the following expected outcomes: support to planning and decision making for research infrastructures at the national (e.g. funding bodies, governments) and European level (e.g. ESFRI) through solid science cases, including expected scientific breakthrough, gap analyses and feasibility/design studies for future research infrastructures or major upgrades of existing ones; a better alignment of the development of the research infrastructure landscape with the advancements of excellent science, frontier research and technology innovation; increased performance, scientific capacity and excellence of the European research infrastructure landscape; new services and access opportunities available to the research community, allowing to better tackle scientific and societal challenges; reduction of environmental (including climate-related) impacts as well as optimisation of resource and energy consumption integrated in the very early phase of development of new research infrastructures or major upgrades of existing ones. Scope: This topic aims at supporting the development of new concepts for the next generation of research infrastructures of European interest[1], single/multi sited, distributed or virtual, that none or few countries might individually be able to implement. All fields of research can be considered. Major upgrades of existing infrastructures may also be considered if the end result is significantly transformative and equivalent to a new infrastructure concept. The possibility to extend the scope of already existing infrastructures and/or integrate in a sustainable way existing pan-European and national capacities to address the specific RI service needs, should indeed be assessed as a first option, identifying what is missing and the necessary new developments. Proposals for RI concept development will tackle all key questions concerning the technical and conceptual feasibility of new or upgraded fully fledged user facilities. In this respect, proposals should address all following aspects: demonstrate relevance in relation to ERA, including to the existing landscape, and the	Any	12 March 2024	23.5M€	4M€	HORIZON Lump Sum Grant			Usual rules for Horizon Europe consortia		https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2024-dev-01-01

Country	Funder name	Type of funder	Title of the call (orig)	Title of the call (EN)	Reference of the call	Short description in English	SRA	Deadline(s)	Budget of the call	Average size of a proposal	Eligible costs (summary)	Funding rate	Percentage of co-funding	Number of participants and partners	Additional information	Website
EU	Horizon Europe: Excellent Science Horizon Europe European Commission (EC)	European	Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods and advanced digital solutions for RIs	Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools and methods and advanced digital solutions for RIs	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01	<p>Scientific communities cannot adequately respond to current research challenges without having access to state-of-the-art scientific instruments and tools. Their constant adaptation, upgrading and innovation, as the underlying technologies develop at a very rapid pace, is critical for providing the optimal conditions for scientific advancements and discoveries in Europe.</p> <p>The aim of this destination is the development of ground-breaking RI technologies, including scientific instruments, tools, methods, and advanced digital solutions, to enable new discoveries and keep RIs in the EU and Associated Countries at the highest level of excellence in science, while also paving the way to innovative solutions to societal challenges and new industrial applications, products and services. New instruments and tools (such as advanced sensors, imaging devices, light source detectors, high-tech developments for accelerators, robots/automated solutions) and advanced digital solutions (e.g. digital twins, data analytics and AI tools, etc.) for RI upgrade, will enable innovative solutions to be found even for the most demanding scientific and societal challenges.</p> <p>Proposals for topics under this destination should set out a credible pathway to contributing to one or several of the following impacts:</p> <p>Enhanced global competitiveness and technological excellence of the EU and Associated Countries in an extremely fast-moving environment through investments into the development, of forward-looking technical instruments and tools for European RIs.</p> <p>Enhanced competitiveness of EU and Associated Countries industry through co-development with industrial actors of advanced RI technologies and technology transfer;</p> <p>Opening up of new areas of research and development of new industrial applications/products;</p> <p>Development of skills of RI staff aligned with the advancements of the RI technologies;</p> <p>Transdisciplinarity, cross-fertilisation and a wider sharing of knowledge and technologies between academia and industry;</p> <p>Wider use of AI in research and enhanced data-driven research across the EU and Associated Countries.</p>	Any	12 March 2024	136M€	15M€					At least 3 world-class research infrastructures, being ESFRI infrastructures, European Research Infrastructures Consortia (ERICs) and/or other world-class research infrastructures of European interest and can include a wider set of RIs. Other technological partners, including industry and SMEs, should also be involved	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-infra-2024-tech-01-01
RO	Ministry for Research, Innovation and Digitalisation	National	Srijin pentru proiecte in domeniul tehnologiilor avansate prin crearea de hub-uri de inovare in domeniul de interes strategic	Support for projects in the field of advanced technologies by creating innovation hubs in areas of strategic interest	Action 1.2 within Priority 1 of the „Smart Growth, Digitization and Financial Instruments” Programme(ERDF)	<p>Within this call, 5 predefined priority projects will be supported with a total budget of 550 mil. Euro:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Romanian Hydrogen and New Technologies HUB - RoHydroHUB National Technology Platform for Semiconductors - PNTS Center for Advanced Studies on River-Sea Systems - DANUBIUS-RO (ESFRI RI) European Infrastructure - Lead Cooled Fast Reactor Technology Demonstrator - ALFRED Romanian Artificial Intelligence HUB - HRIA <p>These projects will support the concentration of the efforts of the academic, research and economic environment, in order to achieve favorable premises for the generation of cores of knowledge and development in advanced and emerging technologies, ensuring a spillover of knowledge and technology, in dedicated fields, of intelligent specialization, in support the development of the national economy.</p>	Any	Future calls to be confirmed	550M€						https://poc.research.gov.ro/ro/articol/4419/cu-privire-lansarea-apelului-de-srijin-pentru-proiecte-in-domeniul-tehnologiilor-avansate-prin-crearea-de-hub-uri-de-inovare-in-domeniul-de-interes-strategic-p1-pocidif#	
DE	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG)	National	Forschungsgroßgeräte nach Art. 91b GG	Major Research Instrumentation Programme		<p>Purpose of Funding:</p> <p>In the “Major Research Instrumentation” funding programme (according to Art. 91b of the Basic Law) the DFG is contributing 50% of the investment costs for major research instrumentation at universities of all kinds (Hochschulen) from a dedicated federal budget as defined in the federal-state agreement on research buildings and major research instrumentation at universities, and national high-performance computing (AV-FGH), decided by the Joint Science Conference (GWK).</p> <p>Successful proposals must be of particular scientific quality and have more than regional significance. The instrumentation must be intended for use predominantly in research, meaning the need for its procurement and use must be justified solely by research. The instrumentation is also permitted to be used in teaching and/or clinical care, but only to a small degree. These areas will not be considered in the assessment and do not contribute to the justification. For further information see: https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/programmes/infrastructure/scientific_instrumentation/funding_opportunities/major_research_instrumentation/index.html</p>	Any	Any time for projects below 7,5M€	Unknown	The gross acquisition cost must be at least €100,000 for universities of applied sciences and at least €200,000 for all other universities.	Major instrumentation is the sum of the components, including accessories, that form a functional state for the intended operational application. An appropriate relationship should exist between the base unit (including software) and its accessories, which can include methodological and measurement-related expansions or supplements that are not directly required for operation.	50%	Provision of 50% co-financing by the federal state or university is required.	Proposals may be submitted by public universities and non-public universities with institutional accreditation.	For projects above 7,5M€ a different process have to be followed.	https://www.dfg.de/en/research_funding/programmes/infrastructure/scientific_instrumentation/funding_opportunities/major_research_instrumentation/index.html
IT	Ministry for Research	National	PNRR	Major Research Instrumentation Programme	Fund for the creation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures”, Action 3.1.1 “ Creation of new IR or strengthening of existing IR involved in the Horizon Europe Scientific Excellence objectives and the establishment of networks”	<p>Promotes the financing of interventions aimed at the creation or strengthening of Research Infrastructures (RI) identified in the PNRR, the National Program of Research Infrastructures, as well as the creation of thematic or multidisciplinary networks of existing IRs, always among those present in the PNRR, in implementation of the investment 3.1. (“Fund for the creation of an integrated system of research and innovation infrastructures”) of Mission 4 (“Education and research”) - Component 2 (“From research to business”) of the PNRR.</p>		EXPIRED	NA	NA	Research infrastructures, personnel	NA	National and regional calls for R&I projects	NA	This kind of project will constitute a resource for the future for the EELISA Alliance in terms of shared facilities because they need to be opened to European partners at the end of the project funding period (March, 2025). As SNS we are involved in EBRAINS (Europe’s Research Infrastructure for Brain Research), SoBigData (Strengthening the Italian RI for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics), while SSSA coordinates BRIEF (Biorobotics Research and Innovation Engineering Facilities); within BRIEF, SSSA and SNS are also constituting a joint lab facility, having additive manufacturing at the micro and nanoscale for robotics as main research topic.	https://www.gea.mur.gov.it/Bandi/IR#definitive